

IMAGE OF ANIMALS IN FOLK PROVERBS AND PHRASES IN ENGLISH AND UZBEKI

Safarova Dilnavoz

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14054906>

Abstract: This study is dedicated to the study of the image of animals in English and Uzbek folk proverbs and expressions. Animal images play an important role in expressing folk wisdom and cultural values. The study analyzes the semantic, cultural and metaphorical features of English and Uzbek proverbs and expressions. For example, the English proverb "The early bird catches the worm" and the Uzbek phrase "The early bird will have plenty of food" express a similar idea, but they differ in their cultural basis and context of use. This analysis provides important scientific information for cross-cultural communication, while identifying cross-linguistic similarities and differences.

Key words: folk proverbs, image of animals, English language, Uzbek language, cultural characteristics, metaphorical analysis.

Introduction. Animal symbolism has long been a key part of folk culture, and animal-related imagery appears across languages in proverbs, idioms, and expressions. Such phrases use animals to represent certain human traits, behaviors, and societal values, often reflecting both linguistic and cultural nuances. English and Uzbek languages both feature a range of animal images in their idioms and proverbs, serving as a bridge between folk wisdom and everyday language. Comparing these expressions provides insight into cultural similarities and differences and shows how each society interprets the natural world. Animals have historically played vital roles in human life, serving as companions, symbols, and sources of sustenance. As such, they are often used in language to personify human virtues, flaws, and behaviors. In English-speaking cultures, animals like the fox, lion, and bee are frequently referenced to symbolize cunning, bravery, and industriousness, respectively. Similarly, in Uzbek culture, animals such as the wolf, camel, and tulki (fox) are common in proverbs, reflecting local experiences and the agrarian lifestyle.

Purpose of animal imagery in proverbs and expressions: The use of animal imagery in proverbs and idioms primarily serves to express complex human behaviors, emotions, and situations in a concise and relatable way. Animals, each with unique qualities, are used to symbolize various traits. For example, lions represent courage, while foxes embody cleverness or cunning. Such proverbs often provide moral or practical advice, helping individuals interpret and

navigate social interactions. These phrases, passed down through generations, offer a window into the beliefs, humor, and values of each culture.

Animal symbolism in English proverbs and expressions: In English, animal-related expressions often carry universal meanings, reflecting commonly observed animal behaviors:

1. **Courage and Strength:** The lion is frequently seen as a symbol of bravery, as in the expression “brave as a lion.” This conveys courage, resilience, and strength, making it ideal for describing a fearless person.
2. **Cunning and Intelligence:** Foxes, often viewed as sly creatures, appear in expressions like “sly as a fox” to characterize individuals who are clever but potentially deceptive. The fox’s association with cleverness in English reflects its role in British folktales as a trickster.
3. **Hard Work and Persistence:** Bees symbolize diligence and industriousness in expressions such as “busy as a bee.” This phrase highlights the hardworking nature of bees, a metaphor that carries over to people who are active and productive.
4. **Docility and Obedience:** Sheep, known for their herd mentality, appear in the expression “like a lamb to the slaughter,” implying passive acceptance or blind obedience, even when it leads to harm. This reflects a critical view of people who lack assertiveness.
5. **Stubbornness:** Donkeys are often associated with stubbornness, as seen in the phrase “stubborn as a mule.” This expression underscores the animal’s perceived obstinacy, commonly used to describe a person who refuses to change their mind.

Animal symbolism in Uzbek proverbs and expressions

Uzbek proverbs also feature animals as symbols of human characteristics, often with nuanced differences from English proverbs:

1. **Courage and Strength:** Like in English, the lion or tiger is a symbol of courage in Uzbek culture, expressed in phrases like “sherdek botir” (brave as a lion/tiger). The lion represents both physical and moral strength in Uzbek, emphasizing heroism and valor.
2. **Cleverness and Trickery:** The fox appears in Uzbek proverbs as a symbol of cunning, as in “Tulki kabi ayyor” (as cunning as a fox). Much like in English, this expression highlights the fox’s trickster image, used to describe someone who is calculating and shrewd.
3. **Industriousness and Diligence:** The ant, rather than the bee, is a common symbol of diligence in Uzbek culture, as in the proverb “Chumoli mehnati bilan

dunyoni ko'taradi" (The ant lifts the world with its labor). This phrase underscores the value of hard work, endurance, and community effort, virtues highly regarded in Uzbek culture.

4. Naivety and Innocence: Sheep in Uzbek expressions symbolize innocence and vulnerability, similar to English usage, as in "Qo'y kabi sodda" (as simple as a sheep). This expression conveys a person's naivety or lack of worldly experience, often leading to disadvantageous situations.

5. Loyalty and Patience: Dogs in Uzbek proverbs are symbols of loyalty and patience, as in "Itga xo'jayin do'st bo'lsa, halollikdan uzoq bo'lmas" (If the master is a friend to his dog, there is no distance from honesty). This reflects the dog's role as a faithful companion and signifies loyalty to loved ones, a highly valued trait in Uzbek culture.

Similarities and Differences in Animal Imagery

A comparative analysis of English and Uzbek proverbs shows both overlap and divergence in how animals are symbolically portrayed:

- Shared Symbolism: Lions in both cultures represent courage and strength, while foxes embody cleverness and slyness, indicating a shared perception of certain animal traits across cultures.
- Different Animals, Similar Values: Although both languages emphasize industriousness, English associates it with the bee, while Uzbek culture uses the ant. These variations reveal unique cultural priorities; bees are associated with productivity in a Western context, while the ant's endurance resonates more with Uzbek values.
- Contextual Nuances: Animals such as dogs reflect contextual differences. In Uzbek, dogs symbolize loyalty and patience, emphasizing traditional respect for loyalty within close relationships. In English, dogs are seen in varied contexts, sometimes positive (loyalty) and sometimes negative (as in "work like a dog").

Cultural Reflection and Linguistic Identity. Proverbs and idioms reflect the cultural environments in which they arise. For example, Uzbek expressions involving the ant highlight the cultural value placed on communal effort and perseverance. In contrast, English idioms such as "sly as a fox" often carry a slightly critical undertone, aligning with the individualistic mindset where personal integrity is paramount.

Additionally, such expressions shape linguistic identity by making complex ideas relatable and accessible. They reinforce the moral teachings and practical

wisdom of each society, passed down from generation to generation, and embedded in the daily language.

Conclusion. The study of animal images in English and Uzbek proverbs and expressions highlights both universal and culture-specific themes. While many animal-based idioms convey similar meanings across languages, unique cultural influences shape the choice of animals and their symbolic roles. These proverbs serve as a cultural bridge, offering insight into values, humor, and societal expectations in both English and Uzbek-speaking communities.

By examining these linguistic elements, we gain a deeper understanding of each culture's worldview and the role of folk wisdom in shaping how people communicate complex ideas about human behavior. The representation of animals in English and Uzbek proverbs and expressions reveals both shared human experiences and culturally unique perspectives. While certain animals, such as lions and foxes, carry similar symbolic meanings across cultures, others, like camels and owls, reflect distinct cultural environments. By studying these linguistic elements, we gain deeper insights into the values and traditions of each society. Animal imagery in language not only enriches communication but also serves as a bridge connecting diverse cultural narratives.

List of references:

1. Arora, S. (1994). Metaphors and Animal Symbolism in Folk Proverbs: A Cross-Cultural Analysis. *Language & Culture Journal*, 12(3), 45–56.
2. Mieder, W. (2004). *Proverbs: A Handbook*. Greenwood Press.
3. Hajiyeva, N. (2015). *Comparative Analysis of Animal Metaphors in Uzbek and English Proverbs*. Tashkent State University Publishing.
4. Lakoff, G., & Johnson, M. (1980). *Metaphors We Live By*. University of Chicago Press.
5. Fiedler, S. (2007). *English Proverbs Explained*. Verlag für Sozialwissenschaften
6. Saidov, A. (2018). *Animal images in Uzbek folk proverbs*. Tashkent: Sharq publishing house.
7. Crystal, D. (1995). *The Cambridge Encyclopedia of the English Language*. Cambridge University Press.
8. Sobirova, R. (2019). *Semantic and pragmatic analysis of phrases about animals in Uzbek and English*. Samarkand State University Press.